

Abstract

Prospect of Antimicrobial Activity of Three Medicinal Herbs for Superficial Infections.

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Abstract

Background: Superficial infections, including both cutaneous and mucocutaneous types, are a current public health problem with global distribution, especially in elders and diabetic patients. One of the main present/future concerns is fungal/bacterial infections by resistant microorganisms such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). This study aimed to test if decoctions and essential oil (EO) of coptidis (*Coptis chinensis*, *Ranunculaceae* family), neem (*Azadirachta indica*, *Meliaceae* family), as well as the EO of manuka (*Leptospermum scoparium*, *Myrtaceae* family) hold antimicrobial activity against prevalent species of microorganisms responsible for superficial infections. **Methods:** Decoction's preparation from rizhoma coptidis and neem seeds using respective dried plant parts in simmering distilled water. EOs were directly acquired from an apotheker. The antimicrobial activity was studied by determining the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), using broth microdilution method, and minimum lethal concentration (MLC) by subculture of MIC plates. **Results and Discussion:** *C. chinensis* EO and decoction demonstrated some antifungal action against the yeasts and dermatophytes tested. Greatest bactericidal effect against *P. acnes* and some action against *S. aureus* was observed. For *A. indica* only EO showed activity against dermatophytes and *P. acnes*. *L. scoparium* EO displayed the broadest antimicrobial spectrum with activity against bacteria, yeasts, and dermatophytes showing greater activity against *P. acnes* and *S. aureus*. **Conclusions:** *C. chinensis* (EO/decoction), EOs of *L. scoparium* and *A. indica* presented in vitro efficacy against both fungal, bacterial or even mixed agents of superficial infections, either by sensitive or resistant strains.

Keywords: Decotion; Essential Oil; Traditional Plants; Antimicrobial Activity; Superficial Infections.

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